

Accessing Data in Health AI Research: Challenges, Insights & Recommendations

Case Study 1 of 3

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AI for Multiple Long-term Conditions
Research Support Facility

Introduction to the RSF & Key Learnings

The **AI for Multiple Long-Term Conditions Research Support Facility** (AIM RSF), a collaborative initiative led by **The Alan Turing Institute** in partnership with **Swansea University**, the **University of Edinburgh** and the **University of Oxford**, oversees eight research consortia across the UK to support and drive culture change in Multiple Long-Term Condition (MLTC) research. By connecting researchers, healthcare professionals, and patients, AIM RSF has reshaped our understanding of MLTCs.

The initiative focuses on five key areas: building robust infrastructure, improving data accessibility, creating a connected research community, engaging with the public, and ensuring lasting impact.

As we approach April 2025, marking the conclusion of this phase of the AIM RSF, we reflect on our achievements and the foundation we've laid for future advancements in MLTC research. This case study, the first in a series of three, shares our journey and offers insights and recommendations for those involved in health data research and AI.

Key Learnings

- A critical gap exists between funding timelines and data access realities. While funders set project deadlines based on expected data availability, accessing health data for research can take up to 18 months, creating significant challenges for project delivery.
- Traditional research data governance frameworks do not align well with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) needs. While data minimisation is important for privacy, AI research often requires larger datasets for effective model training - creating a tension that needs addressing through flexible governance structures.
- While collaborations between multiple institutions strengthen research capabilities, they create additional complexity in data licensing agreements and governance processes. This is particularly evident in cases like CPRD, where managing multi-institutional access requires new approaches to data sharing.
- Standard computing resources provided by Trusted Research Environments (TREs) often prove insufficient for advanced AI and ML models. Researchers often require specialised computing infrastructure, such as GPUs, which need bespoke builds or skill sets.
- Many research teams underestimate the time, resources, and expertise needed for data hosting and preparation. This leads to unexpected needs for upskilling and creates additional pressure on project timelines and budgets.
- The creation of shared resources (such as synthetic datasets for training) and centralised coordination can reduce the burden on individual research teams. This includes standardising approaches to data security, infrastructure setup, and data cleaning steps across institutions.

Introduction

Access to data is critical to the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) methodologies in health research, but gaining access to this data is not always straightforward. Often, researchers have to overcome many hurdles. The National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) awarded funding towards research using advanced data science and AI to study people living with Multiple Long-Term Health Conditions (MLTC) and identify new ways to prevent and treat these conditions. This funding has led to the establishment of the AIM RSF and a wider AI for Multiple Long-Term Conditions Programme (AIM) consortium funded as collaborative research programmes.

Through discussions with the researchers that make up the AIM consortia and health data providers, the AIM RSF sought to identify challenges with data access in the context of health AI research, articulate why these challenges occur, and offer possible solutions to be used in future research. These resultant recommendations should be considered when organising and carrying out future research in this field.

Identification of Suitable Data

One of the primary challenges faced by research consortia, particularly in the context of researching MLTCs, is identifying the most suitable data for their research. In the UK, a wealth of de-identified health record data is available through various data providers, but accessing and navigating these resources can be complex. Data can be disseminated through a range of methods, from physical access (which is increasingly being phased out due to recommendations from the [Goldacre Review](#)) to secure access via Trusted Research Environments (TREs). However, even understanding what data is available poses a challenge, as there is significant variation in data collections, access methods, and the information provided by different platforms. While efforts like the [Health Data Research Gateway](#) and [UK Data Service](#) aim to streamline the cataloguing of health data, there is still a need for better tools to assist research consortia in determining which datasets are most viable for MLTC-related research. Often, basic data availability information can be found on websites and catalogues, but details about governance pathways, funding requirements, and metadata may not be as readily accessible. To address this gap, the AIM RSF has developed a document to provide a clear, snapshot overview of relevant data infrastructure for MLTC research.

Resource Highlight: This "Research Data and Infrastructure Horizon Scan" compiles publicly available information into a comprehensive brochure, offering initial clarity on data availability, access procedures, cost implications, and metadata details. This resource aims not only to assist MLTC researchers but also to support broader research groups seeking access to UK health data.

Learn more about the "Research Data and Infrastructure Horizon Scan"

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Data Access Challenges

A common challenge encountered by the AIM research consortia was the delay in accessing the necessary datasets required for their work. These delays are primarily due to the stringent governance procedures enforced by data providers to ensure the responsible and secure use of sensitive data in research. While these governance frameworks are crucial for safeguarding privacy and ethical standards, they do not always align well with the methodologies and requirements of AI and machine learning (ML) research. Specifically, research consortia often require large-scale datasets that extend beyond the immediate cohort of individuals directly experiencing MLTCs.

This larger dataset is essential for training AI models, enabling tasks such as population cohort creation, risk prediction, and intervention suggestion. The challenge arises from the tension between the principles of data minimisation, ensuring only necessary data is used and the need for broader data sets to enable robust AI research. To overcome this, there is a pressing need to reconsider governance structures, ensuring they are flexible enough to accommodate the diverse use cases inherent in AI research, without automatically rejecting the broader data requirements essential for generating accurate models and impactful interventions.

Funding and Data Access Alignment

The experiences of the AIM consortia have highlighted a significant disconnect between the terms and timelines set by funding bodies and the often complex and time-consuming processes required to access data from providers and custodians. For instance, many of the AIM-funded programmes faced significant delays, with some requiring up to 18 months to gain access to the specific data needed for their research. Funding bodies typically set project timelines and allocate funds based on expected data availability, but these timelines often fail to account for the unpredictable and sometimes severe delays in accessing data; delays that are beyond the control of researchers. Data, particularly in the context of de-identified health records, is provided as a service by a variety of organisations across the UK. However, due to the lack of standardisation in data access pathways, timelines, and review processes, large multi-institutional projects involving AI and machine learning are particularly vulnerable to delays.

In many cases, data access timelines are estimated, but these estimates can vary widely, as each request faces unique challenges. Delays in data access or funding deployment may prevent a project from receiving the necessary data on time, thereby hindering the completion of deliverables outlined in funding applications. Projects with shorter timelines or more rigid funding profiles are especially at risk, as they may not have the flexibility to adjust to delays. In the worst-case scenario, these delays can derail a project entirely.

To address this issue, the AIM RSF recommends that funding bodies provide more detailed information, such as the [Horizon Scan](#) and similar documentation, to grant applicants. Additionally, funding bodies should facilitate direct communication between researchers and data providers to streamline data access once funding is awarded. While it is impossible to guarantee timely data access due to the inherent complexities of data governance and compliance, fostering better communication between funders and data providers would improve clarity for researchers and help align data access with the needs of projects which use AI methods and where multiple institutions are collaborating towards the same research goal.

An Exemplar: CPRD

The connections and collaborations the AIM RSF facilitated with the AIM research consortia led to summarising common data access challenges. These challenges were discussed with data providers and funders, advocating for community-level solutions that go beyond one research group or programme. Encouraging and maintaining open communication among the multiple stakeholders involved in research is essential for enhancing research governance and ensuring effective collaboration. Producing open and accessible resources is crucial to accelerating research progress.

This section explores data access challenges related to one specific data provider, the [Clinical Practice Research Datalink](#) (CPRD), and how the AIM programme (AI for Multiple-long term conditions) helped to promote new ways of working to overcome particular challenges. CPRD is one of the largest providers of anonymised patient health data for research, covering GP data across the UK and linked to a range of other health related data. AIM research consortia all identified similar barriers when attempting to access CPRD data, which are reflective of broader issues in health research data access. These include long application processing times, complex data governance procedures, and a lack of clarity regarding timelines and costs.

CPRD and other data providers require researchers to pay for data access, often based on a cost-recovery model that covers data processing (anonymisation, validation, quality control), governance and access infrastructure. While delays are common in data access, the AIM consortia experienced longer-than-anticipated waiting times, which in turn delayed the progress of their research. The discrepancies between the expectations set by funding bodies and the realities of data access timelines have highlighted the need for more streamlined processes and better communication between funders, researchers, and data providers.

Summarised below, are the key challenges the AIM RSF identified with CPRD data access, followed by responses and solutions. These offer valuable insights into the systemic barriers that research groups face when trying to access health data. The issues identified, and subsequent learnings, are not just relevant for CRPD but also other health data providers.

1. Challenges - Data Governance & Study Justification

- A strength of the AIM programme lies in its collaboration between multiple institutions to deliver large-scale research projects. However, the licence agreements negotiated between CPRD and these multiple institutions proved to be more complex and time-consuming than anticipated.
- CPRD found that many of these large research programmes lacked sufficient specificity for their data governance review, with protocols submitted for approval often encompassing both hypothesis generation and testing. Furthermore, the use of AI, along with requests for larger data subsets than usual, posed additional challenges with respect to data minimisation. Researchers struggled to access adequate detail regarding the datasets, which made it difficult to justify the need for specific data subsets. When adjustments were required to the requested data subsets, delays ensued, resulting in additional work for both the researchers and CPRD.

2. Challenges - Data Hosting and Data Preparation

CPRD sent the datasets as files to each approved institution. With these files, each institution developed individual approaches to data security and infrastructure setup, and data cleaning steps. More collaboration between researchers, and more centralised resources from data providers, are needed to streamline and harmonise methods to avoid unnecessary differences and repetition of work. Research groups did not always anticipate the time, resources and expertise required for hosting and preparing CPRD datasets, particularly for large data subsets.

Any delays caused to data access, hosting or pre-processing brings stress to research groups as this can require unexpected upskilling and cuts into their timelines for delivering on their research grants. Furthermore, needing data access for longer periods, due to delays caused with data hosting and pre-processing, will cost more money for research groups.

What solutions were found?

These commonly experienced challenges were discussed with researchers, clinicians, data scientists and infrastructure specialists, data providers and funders to help to develop solutions for data access within healthcare data.

- CPRD implemented third party agreements to facilitate data sharing between multiple institutions, with more refinement on data governance processes to come.
- When protocols requesting data were too broad for CPRD's typical review and audit process, protocols could be split in two. CPRD acknowledged the links between protocols whilst ensuring the same data is not paid for twice by the researchers.
- CPRD is moving towards a new model of data access, via a [Trusted Research Environment \(TRE\)](#). Feedback from the AIM programme and the RSF has formed some of the core design principles of this TRE.
- AIM RSF members have been invited to join CPRD advisory boards (e.g. Scientific Advisory Group).

The RSF advocated for the use-cases of [CPRD's medium fidelity synthetic datasets](#) to the AIM programme. These datasets mirror the structure of real CPRD datasets and can be a useful resource whilst waiting for governance approvals.

- These medium-fidelity synthetic datasets are now free!
- CPRD has launched a specific teaching licence based on synthetic data to facilitate the development and dissemination of training materials.
- The RSF team created an [openly available training resource](#) using synthetic datasets to help researchers become familiar with the structure and format of CPRD data files, as well as software and infrastructure guides. Learnings have guided other projects that RSF members are involved in, for example [Turing-Roche](#).
- Further conversations between CPRD and the RSF members on how dataset training can be further facilitated for the research community. For instance, an aspiration would be to have a 'sandbox' TRE space that has fewer barriers to access, where researchers can learn about the CPRD datasets via tutorials written on synthetic datasets. However, this would come with operating costs.

Resource Highlight: AIM RSF data wranglers have developed clear documentation, analytical pipelines, and workflows using CPRD's synthetic dataset to support researchers working with real CPRD data. The workflow is open-source and can be accessed [here](#). It can also be cited via [Zenodo](#).

Optimising Skillsets for Using Complex Data in MLTC Research

Once data is granted, leveraging it effectively requires the right skill sets and technologies. Health data in the UK is highly diverse, necessitating research teams with expertise across multiple coding languages and a robust understanding of data curation techniques. Analysts with skills in SQL, R, or Python are vital for managing relational databases, linking multiple tables, and preparing data for analysis. Research teams must also navigate varied clinical terminology and data formats, often investing significant time in mapping code lists and porting algorithms between environments to create reproducible pipelines.

The AIM RSF has facilitated such efforts, including developing an [R package](#) to map publicly available health metadata onto research domains, curating openly available [drug code lists](#) with the OPTIMAL consortium, and [highlighting challenges and best practices relating to clinical coding in the wider MLTC research community](#). These efforts demonstrate how centralised coordination can alleviate the burden on individual research teams, enabling more efficient and effective analyses.

Optimising Technical Setups for Using Complex Data in MLTC Research

From a technical standpoint, optimising the research environment early in the project is critical. The computational requirements for deploying advanced AI and ML models often exceed the default resources provided by TREs. The SAIL Databank, one of the national data providers listed in the Horizon Scan providing data for Wales was used by four of the AIM consortia. Using the base compute provided by the SAIL TRE itself was not sufficient for AIM researchers to run large models, and so a Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) solution was established to provide an upscale in compute for analysts wanting to deploy models needing more intense runtimes. Given such compute is often expensive to commission and run, more coordination needs to be established to provide centralised or federated compute options for research consortia who wish to deploy complex analyses in addition to standard statistics, particularly given the upsurge in AI and ML modelling and analytical methods.

Resource Highlight: [mapmetadata R package](#) which maps publicly available health metadata onto research domains. This mapmetadata package uses structural metadata files, downloaded from the Health Data Research Gateway. It also it helps the researcher address the question "Which variables map onto with my research domains? (e.g. socioeconomic, childhood adverse events, diagnoses, culture and community)". The R package was peer-reviewed by [rOpenSci](#) and its documentation can be accessed [here](#).

Resource Highlight: Drug code lists are available as open-source on [GitHub](#). This repository has been set up to share drug lists across NIHR's AIM projects. Currently, the lists originate from the AIM Consortium OPTIMAL, based in Birmingham. A paper and poster have been created to review published methodologies, discussing current understanding and potential challenges in coding clinical data, selecting data sources (e.g. electronic health records), and ensuring the validity of decision-making processes. These can be accessed on [Zenodo](#).

Conclusions

The challenges and opportunities outlined in this case study highlight the need for coordinated efforts to optimise the use of health data for AI and MLTC research. Access to suitable datasets, alignment between funding timelines and data availability, streamlined governance frameworks, and the development of robust technical and analytical skillsets are all critical factors in ensuring the success of research programmes in this field.

Efforts to address these challenges must focus on fostering better communication and collaboration between researchers, data providers, and funders. Standardisation of processes, enhanced data infrastructure, and the promotion of open, accessible resources can accelerate research progress while maintaining ethical standards and data security.

Moreover, initiatives that support the development of specialised skillsets, efficient technical setups, and collaborative environments will empower researchers to harness the full potential of AI and data science in addressing the complexities of MLTCs. By investing in these areas, the broader research community can pave the way for innovative solutions and impactful advancements in health data science.

Ultimately, these actions will ensure that health research is better equipped to meet the demands of an evolving landscape, enabling researchers to deliver meaningful outcomes for patients and healthcare systems alike.

Through the Research Support Facility (RSF) model, the AIM RSF amplified the voices of individual researchers and research consortia, identifying common challenges in data access and offering actionable solutions where possible. By engaging in direct constructive dialogue with data providers such as CPRD, the AIM RSF gained valuable insight into perspectives and encouraged a collaborative, future-oriented approach to improving data access and governance. While goals between research groups and data providers were often aligned, many ad hoc solutions to immediate challenges were identified, with an understanding that longer-term systemic improvements are essential.

Lessons Learned

The AIM RSF and its collaborative approach have highlighted the value of partnership, adaptability, and proactive problem-solving in overcoming challenges. By sharing insights and aligning efforts across stakeholders, significant strides have been made in addressing both immediate and systemic issues related to data access and research infrastructure.

Gratitude is extended to the AIM research consortia, data providers, and funding bodies for their dedication and collaboration. Together, a strong foundation has been set for advancing MLTC research and ensuring that innovative tools and methodologies are effectively deployed to improve healthcare outcomes.

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